

Wear Behavior of Boron Carbide Powder Reinforced Coating on AISI 4140 Produced by Plasma Transferred Arc

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Abstract: Moving parts that are essential to life are subject to wear and friction. Coatings, lubrication and heat treatment are some operations conducted to reduce these effects and prolong part life. Plasma Transferred Arc coating is an important coating method for hard coating. It is used in various industrial applications such as automotive valves, glass and ceramic molds and plastic extrusion dies. In PTA powder content that is used for coating is an important point of research. In this study microstructure and wear behavior of AISI 4140 steel surface coated by Boron Carbide was inspected. Ekabor II powder that contains Boron Carbide was mixed with a Nickel base to produce coating powder. Wear tests were conducted on a Ball-on-Disk device with circular geometry. Optical Microscopy was used to characterize microstructure of coating layer formed on the surface of AISI 4140. It was found that although Boron Carbide content has positive improvements these improvements lessen after 10% Ekabor by weight in coating.

Keywords: Boron Carbide, PTA, tribology, coating

1. INTRODUCTION

Parts used in industrial applications are subject to friction and wear. Reduction of these effects is an important research field. There are various methods used in reducing these effects. Lubrication is the most used of these methods. However when lubrication is not enough surface modification techniques are used. Plasma Transferred Arc process is an important surface modification technique with its high temperature (up to 30000K), relatively ease of use characteristics [1]. PTA technique with its very high coating thicknesses, less thermal stress on material and high energy density is used on glass and ceramic molds, automotive valves, petro-chemical vanes and lamination cylinders and plastic extrusion molds and screws [2]. PTA process resembles Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW) process. Electrical arc is generated between electrode and work piece. The difference between PTA and GTAW is PTA electrode is in torch body so plasma arc is separated from shield gas. Generated plasma is compressed through a copper nozzle and high speed and high temperatures are obtained. A coating powder is carried by carrier gas and surface is coated. A simple schematic drawing of PTA torch with powder feeder is shown at *Figure 1*. PTA coating powders are composed of a base and additional materials. Base is usually composed of Cobalt and Nickel powders. WC, NiCrWc, Cr₃C₂, TiC, VC powders are usually used for steels [3].

Figure 1 Powder Feed PTA torch schematic drawing [4]

2. Materials and Methods

In this study Ekabor II that contains 5% B_4C , 5% KBF_4 and 90% SiC [5] was mixed with Nickel in weight ratios given at **Table 1** to produce PTA powder. Powder was put on 100x40x20mm AISI 4140 steel with a 1 mm depth 3 mm width channel. Sodium Silicate was used for binding agent and samples were left to dry for 24 hours in a shaded moisture controlled environment. At the end of 24 hour period samples were preheated at 300°C and PTA coating is conducted at 100A current with a 3mm electrode and working distance of 4mm. Argon was used as shielding and plasma gas at 25 l/min and 1.0 l/min flow rates respectively.

Code	Nickel to Ekabor II Ratio
A1	4%
A2	6%
A3	8%
A4	10%
A5	12%

Table 1 PTA Powder Mixtures

Metallography tests were conducted on cross sections of coating. Samples for metallography tests were prepared by standard sample preparation techniques and etched with 2% Nital etchant for 40s.

Vickers microhardness measurements were obtained using a Future Tech microhardness tester with 100gf load at 10s indentation time.

Ball-on-Disc wear were conducted on CSM tribometer at 3N load, 2.5 cm/s speed for 80m. Samples were ground to 0.6 μ m average surface roughness value prior to test. 3mm diameter WC balls were used as the counterpart and all tests were conducted at 25°C ambient temperature and 35% relative humidity. Wear track profiles were measured using Mitutoyo SJ-400 surface profilometer. Ball-on-Disc test results were analyzed using trib R package developed by authors [6].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Microstructure

A panoramic image obtained from metallography sample is given at **Figure 2**. Inspection of this image clearly shows that areas with different phase structure are produced through PTA coating. **Figure 3** shows metallography images of every sample and hardness values of measured from different areas. The lighter areas have hardness over 500HV.

Figure 2 Panoramic view of A4 50x

Figure 3 Samples etched with Nital 2% for 40s

Figures 4,5 and 6 show sample SEM images and EDS results of coatings A1, A3 and A4. These images were chosen as a better representation of material properties of coatings. It can be seen that A1 has V in coating but A3 and A4 has no alloying material from AISI 4140. Also A3 has high Si and C content however A4 has more Ni and no C content in the coating.

a) SEM image of sample A1

Elt.	Line	Intensity (c/s)	Error 2-sig	Conc	Units	
C	Ka	6.23	1.579	1.600	wt.%	
Si	Ka	9.04	1.902	0.437	wt.%	
V	Ka	4.89	1.398	0.132	wt.%	
Fe	Ka	0.136	23.631	90.627	wt.%	
Ni	Ka	72.72	5.393	7.204	wt.%	
				100.00	wt.%	Tot
				0		

b) EDS analysis of point 1

Figure 4 SEM and EDS analysis of sample A1

a) SEM image of sample A3

Elt.	Line	Intensity (c/s)	Error 2-sig	Conc	Units	
C	Ka	5.02	1.424	938	wt.%	
Si	Ka	14.70	2.424	515	wt.%	
Fe	Ka	2,055.12	28.662	98.3 38	wt.%	
Ni	Ka	2.85	1.068	209	wt.%	
				100. 000	wt.%	Tot

b) EDS analysis of area 1

Figure 5 SEM and EDS analysis of sample A3

a) SEM image of sample A4

Elt.	Line	Intensity (c/s)	Error 2-sig	Conc	Units	
C	Ka	0.00	0	0	wt.%	
Si	Ka	3.35	1.157	1.082	wt.%	
Fe	Ka	342.13	11.696	95.933	wt.%	
Ni	Ka	6.93	1.665	2.984	wt.%	
				100.000	wt.%	Total

b) EDS analysis of area 1

Figure 6 SEM and EDS analysis of sample A4

3.2 Wear Test

Average coefficient of friction values are between 0.37879 and 0.43259 as seen from **Figure 4**. Coefficient of friction values are obtained from friction force versus distance graphs of samples with WC ball which is given at **Figure 8**.

Figure 7 Average Coefficient of Friction of samples

Figure 8 Friction Force versus Distance graph from Ball-on-Disk test

Figure 7 and **Figure 8** show that increasing B₄C ratio higher than 10% increases coefficient of friction. 4% and 10% gives better coefficient of friction values.

Figure 9 Cross section profiles of wear track of coatings

Figure 9 shows cross sectional wear track profile of samples. *Figure 10* shows wear track volume of samples calculated from wear track measurements. These figures show that the least wear was observed at samples with 4% and 10% addition of Ekabor II.

Figure 10 Wear Track Volume of samples

4. CONCLUSION

In this study effects of B₄C addition in PTA process was observed. The microstructure, hardness and wear properties of coatings were investigated. Microstructure and EDS analysis show that when Nickel content in the coating decreases wear increases. Although Nickel isn't a hardfacing material thus doesn't affect friction coefficient, Nickel decreases abrasive wear and lack of Nickel in coating increases material loss to wear.

EDS analysis show that A1 has more carbide forming elements such as Si and V in coating. This explains the reason of low coefficient of friction and low wear track volume. As EDS analysis of A3 shows a high percentage of Si content in coating it is expected that wear behaviour will be better. Ball on disk test results indicate an opposite trend. High SiC content resulted in high abrasive wear and resulted in inferior wear behaviour. This is a result in PTA process and process parameters should be controlled to avoid this formation.

As a result the following conclusions were drawn. Ekabor II as a medium for adding B₄C was found to be suitable for PTA process. Increasing Ekabor II ratio after 10% addition results in a negative effect. The best weight ratios for PTA coating is 4% and 10% Ekabor II addition.

5. Acknowledgement

This study was funded by TUBITAK 2211 and Eskisehir Osmangazi University Scientific Research Commission Project 2014-599.

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